

First Record of *Fukuyoa* sp. (Gambierdiscoideae) in the Northeastern Region of Términos Lagoon, Campeche, Mexico

Fig. 1. Map of sampling stations at Términos Lagoon, Campeche, Mexico. The station where *Fukuyoa* sp. was found is circled in red.

Términos Lagoon is a region of substantial economic relevance due to its fisheries, petroleum activities, and high biodiversity, which includes dolphins, manatees, waterbirds, crocodiles, and jaguars, among other species. Situated in the southern Gulf of Mexico along the coastal zone of Campeche, it is recognized as the second-largest coastal lagoon in Mexico. The system maintains two connections with the Bay of Campeche: the Carmen Inlet to the northwest and the Puerto Real Inlet to the northeast.

The Puerto Real inlet is characterized by a significant marine influence, which sustains extensive seagrass meadows. These communities are primarily composed of *Thalassia testudinum* (turtlegrass), *Syringodium filiforme* (manatee grass), *Halodule wrightii* (shoal grass), and *Halophila engelmannii* (star grass). These meadows provide a specialized ecological niche for diverse microalgal assemblages, including epiphytic and benthic dinoflagellates. Therefore, this study aimed to document the presence of benthic toxic dinoflagellates (BTD) in the Términos Lagoon, Campeche, Mexico.

As part of the research project “Ecological Characterization of Coastal Environments of Mexico – UAM-ICD.CBS, 2023–2026,” a comprehensive sampling campaign was conducted at 27 stations across the Términos Lagoon in May 2024 (Fig. 1). Water samples were collected using a 2.5 L Van Dorn bottle, from which 500 mL subsamples were taken to measure physicochemical parameters specifically salinity, temperature, and pH using a Hanna multiparameter probe. For biological analysis, horizontal tows were performed at each station using a conical net with a 60 µm mesh size; the collected samples were stored in 250 mL bottles and fixed with a 4% formalin solution. In the laboratory, subsamples mounted on glass slides with coverslips were examined under a Zeiss-Axiolab brightfield microscope at 40x magnification. Additionally, Calcofluor White staining was employed to observe thecal plate patterns via epifluorescence microscopy (Zeiss-Axiolab) using the same magnification. Morphological identification of benthic dinoflagellates was performed using the specialized descriptions provided by Hoppenrath et al. (2023) [1].

In the northeastern region of the Términos Lagoon, specifically at the Puerto Real pier (Fig. 1), the presence of a benthic dinoflagellate belonging to the genus *Fukuyoa* is reported for the first time. Cells ($n = 14$) present a well-defined ovoid shape that is anteroposteriorly compressed, with a diameter ranging from 40–60.6 µm and a transdiameter (width) of 36.1–51.3 µm (Fig. 2). They exhibit a highly compressed ventral view, a descending cingulum, and a well-defined sulcus. Notably, *Fukuyoa* sp. was recorded in the water column; this occurrence may be attributed to the environment at the Puerto Real pier zone (E25), which features seagrass meadows dominated by *Thalassia testudinum* and calcareous-sandy sediments, under temperatures ranging from 31–32 °C, salinities between 33–38.9, and shallow depths of 0.5–1 m.

Currently, four species are recognized within the genus *Fukuyoa*: *F. ruetzleri* (M.A. Faust, Litaker, Vandersea, Kibler, W.C. Holland & P.A. Tester) F. Gómez, D.X. Qiu, R.M. Lopes & Senjie Lin; *F. yasumotoi* (M.J. Holmes) F. Gómez, D.X. Qiu, R.M. Lopes & Senjie Lin; *F. paulensis* F. Gómez, D.J. Qiu, R.M. Lopes & Senjie Lin; and *F. korensis* Zhun Li, J.S. Park, N.S. Kang, K.-W. Lee & H.H. Shin [2– 4]. Based on the thecal plate arrangement of the cells found in the Términos Lagoon, and following the specific tabulation formula proposed by [2] (Po, 3', 7'', 6C, 5'', 1p, 2'''), the specimen morphologically conforms to *Fukuyoa paulensis*. This preliminary identification is supported by the globular cell shape, cingular displacement, and the distinctive configuration of the apical pore complex (Po) and the 1'plate. However, since the smaller cingular and sulcal plates) require further verification and given the well-documented cryptic diversity within this genus, molecular sequencing is strongly recommended to provide a reliable species-level identification for this dinoflagellate.

Dinoflagellates belonging to the genus *Fukuyoa* inhabit benthic and epibenthic environments and are commonly associated with macroalgae, sediments, corals, seagrasses, and occasionally the water column, in tropical coastal waters such as those of the Términos Lagoon [2]. Studies conducted

Fig. 2. (A–B). *Fukuyoa* sp. in ventral view. (C). Dorsal view. (D). Antapical view showing plates S. d. p., 1'', 1'''. (E–F). Ventral view showing plates 1', 1'', 2'', 7'', S. d. p., 1'', 1'''. (G–H). Antapical view showing plates 1p, 2''', 3''', 1''', 2'''. Scale bars = 20 µm.

in Australia [6] recorded *F. paulensis* at temperatures of 27.6 °C, salinities of 29.2, and a pH of 8.5. In Mexico, *F. yasumotoi* was previously reported in the Sian Ka'an Biosphere Reserve at depths of 0.4 to 2.5 m, temperatures between 25 and 28 °C, and a salinity of 22 [7], environmental conditions where both temperature and salinity were lower than those recorded in this study.

The ecological, economic, and public health relevance of *Fukuyoa* lies in its status as a potentially toxic genus. Three of the four known species within this genus *Fukuyoa paulensis*, *F. ruetzleri*, and *F. yasumotoi* can produce ciguatoxins (CTXs), a group of potent neurotoxins responsible for ciguatera poisoning (CFP). In humans, CFP symptoms range from gastrointestinal and neurological disorders to death in severe cases [5]. However, toxic profiles vary; for instance, while these three species are recognized toxin producers, such capacity has not yet been demonstrated for *F. koreensis*. Globally, ciguatera-producing dinoflagellates represent a major public health concern, causing an estimated 25,000 to 500,000 poisonings annually [8].

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